

ALTERNATIVE FINANCIAL SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN: STATE AND PROSPECTS

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Abstract: *This article provides an overview of the main directions of development of alternative financial systems in Uzbekistan, highlighting their importance for sustainable economic development and social stability. In the future, it is necessary to continue working on improving the legislative framework and infrastructure to support these initiatives.*

Keywords: *Alternative financial systems, Islamic finance, microfinance, digitalization of finance, Uzbekistan, financial inclusion, green bonds, Oson, IMAN, agriculture*

In recent years, Uzbekistan has been actively developing alternative financial systems aimed at diversifying sources of financing and increasing the availability of financial services for various segments of the population. The key areas in this area are Islamic finance, microfinance, and digitalization of financial services. These initiatives contribute to improving financial inclusion, stimulate entrepreneurial activity and support the sustainable development of the country's economy.

Microfinance in Uzbekistan plays a key role in supporting small and medium-sized businesses, especially in agriculture. Many farmers and entrepreneurs face difficulties in obtaining traditional bank loans due to the lack of collateral or credit history. Microfinance organizations provide loans on more flexible terms, which contributes to the development of entrepreneurship and improving the living standards of the population. In 2024, the United Nations Development Program in Uzbekistan published a study on alternative financial mechanisms in agriculture. It analyzes existing government support measures and offers recommendations for improving the financing system for the agricultural sector, including the introduction of energy and water-saving technologies.

Digitalization of financial services in Uzbekistan contributes to increasing accessibility and convenience for users. An example of successful implementation of digital financial services is the Oson electronic payment system, which allows users to pay for various goods and services, as well as transfer funds between Uzcard and HUMO cards. Since its launch in 2017, Oson has attracted over 500,000 users and continues to evolve, offering new features and expanding its range of services. Digitalization also promotes financial inclusion by allowing people from remote regions to access financial services without having to visit physical bank branches.

Islamic finance is based on the principles of Sharia, which exclude interest income (riba) and encourage investment in real assets. In Uzbekistan, the development of Islamic banking received a significant boost after the signing of an agreement with the international consulting company IFAAS in 2022, aimed at developing legislation for the introduction of Islamic banking in the country. Within the framework of Islamic banking in Uzbekistan, various financial instruments operate, such as murabaha (trade finance), sukuk (Islamic bonds), ijara (leasing) and takaful (insurance). These tools provide an alternative to traditional banking products, meeting the ethical and moral standards of the Muslim economy. An example of the successful implementation of Islamic financial technologies is the startup IMAN, which in 2022 attracted 1 million US dollars from investment funds from Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, the United States and Singapore. IMAN offers a marketplace, installment and investment service.

The reasons for the interest in Islamic finance in Uzbekistan are: Socio-cultural factor: Uzbekistan is a Muslim country where more than 90% of the population professes Islam. This creates

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a natural demand for financial products that comply with Sharia law (for example, without interest — riba). Diversification of the financial system: Uzbekistan has been actively working to attract foreign investment and expand the financial market since 2016 (gradual reforms after the change of the country's leadership). Islamic finance is one of the ways to diversify and increase the sustainability of the economy. Regional example: Neighboring countries such as Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and Azerbaijan already have Islamic banks or Islamic financing instruments. Uzbekistan strives to keep up with regional trends.) Support from international organizations: The Islamic Development Bank (IsDB) actively cooperates with Uzbekistan, investing in infrastructure and social projects, as well as promoting Islamic.

Let's present analytical comparative data on the types of financing in table 1 for 2023 and 2024 in comparison. Microfinance and Islamic finance in Uzbekistan (2023-2024)

Table 1 – Microfinance in dynamics

Indicator	The year 2023	The year 2024	Change (%)
Total loan volume	8.6 trillion soums	16 trillion soums	+85%
Net profit	833 billion soums	1 billion soums	+20%
The share of online loans	29%	54%	+86%
Average loan size	10–50 million soums	10–50 million soums	—
Percentage of individuals	94%	94%	—
Share of legal	6%	6%	—
The maximum size of a microloan	50 million soums	100 million soums	+100%
Number of MFIs	84	100	+19%
Number of branches	185	236	+27%

Thus, the volume of lending by microfinance organizations (MFIs) in 2023 amounted to 8.6 trillion. soums. The total volume of loans in 2024 increased to 16 trillion. soums, which is 85% more than in 2023. Of these, 14.4 trillion. soums are made up of loans issued by MFIs, and 1.8 trillion soums by pawnshops. In the lending structure, individuals account for 94% of the total lending volume (15.2 trillion soums), while legal entities account for 6% of the total lending volume (963 billion soums). The share of online loans was 29% in 2023, and in 2024 the share of online loans increased to 54%, indicating a significant increase in digitalization in the microfinance sector.

Also in 2023, amendments were made to the legislation increasing the maximum amount of microloans for individuals from 50 to 100 million soums. In 2024, a Program was adopted to increase the availability of microfinance services for 2024-2026, aimed at increasing the volume of the microfinance market by at least 5 times and reaching more than 1 million business entities.

There were no Islamic banks and Islamic financial products in Uzbekistan in 2023. And already in 2024, the Central Bank of Uzbekistan developed a bill on Islamic banking, which was submitted to parliament. A regulation on Islamic financial services for microfinance organizations has also been developed. 12 banks in Uzbekistan, including Agrobank, Uzpromstroybank, Mikrokreditbank, Ipak Yuli and others, began providing murabakh services through credit lines of the Islamic Corporation for the Development of the Private Sector. Trast Muamalat, a subsidiary of Trustbank, provides Islamic leasing services.

Table 2 - Comparative table: Microfinance and Islamic finance in Uzbekistan (2023-2024)

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Indicator	Microfinance (2023)	Microfinance (2024)	Islamic Finance (2023)	Islamic Finance (2024)
Total loan volume	8,6 trillion soums	16 trillion soums	—	—
The share of online loans	29%	54%	—	—
The maximum size of a microloan	50 million soums	100 million soums	—	—
Number of MFIs	84	100	—	—
Number of Islamic banks	0	0	0	0
Legislative framework	—	Under development	—	Development
Practical implementation	implemented	implemented	—	The beginning of the provision

Thus, the microfinance sector has demonstrated significant growth in 2024, especially in the field of online lending. The increase in the maximum amount of microloans and the development of digital platforms contribute to improving access to finance for the population. Although the legislative framework and practical implementation of Islamic financial services began in 2024, the sector is still in its infancy. It is recommended to accelerate the adoption of relevant regulations and expand the practical implementation of Islamic financial products.

The development of alternative financial systems in Uzbekistan opens up new opportunities for economic growth and social stability. However, for the successful implementation of these initiatives, a number of challenges must be overcome, including improving the legislative framework, increasing financial literacy among the population, and developing infrastructure to support digital financial services. In particular, for the effective implementation of "green" financial instruments, such as green bonds, it is necessary to develop appropriate standards and valuation methodologies, as well as create an institutional structure that supports these initiatives. Islamic finance in Uzbekistan is still in its infancy, but the interest of the state, international partners and the population forms a favorable basis for their development. Over the next 5-7 years, we can expect the emergence of a full-fledged Islamic banking infrastructure, especially if an appropriate legal act is adopted and an active information campaign is conducted.

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